

Potential of rice stubble in spreading tungro in West Bengal, India

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An experiment was conducted to determine the potential of rice stubble for spreading tungro virus disease in rice fields. Taichung Native 1 (TN1) seedlings were grown under heavy tungro inoculum pressure, which infected the plants markedly. After harvest clumps of stubble of the infected plants were carefully uprooted. Some intact clumps were placed in pots. The others were chopped, mixed with soil, and placed in pots. The intact stubbles were then tested at 15-day intervals for the presence of the virus.

Test seedlings of TN1 were transplanted into the pots containing the soil-stubble mixture under insect-proof conditions and then tested 10 days later. Freshly emerged *Nephotettix virescens* collected from the rearing chambers were released and kept on the seedlings for several days. The seedlings were then observed for 20 days.

A field experiment was conducted to study the efficiency of stubble as the

Table 1. Transmission of rice tungro virus from Taichung Native 1 (TN1) stubble of different ages. West Bengal, India.

Stubble age at acquisition feeding time (days from harvest)	Time of transmission	Transmission in seedlings (%)
<i>Boro season 1977^a</i>		
15	1st wk, May	20.0
30	3d wk, May	13.3
4s	1st wk, June	13.3
60	3d wk, June	6.6
7s	1st wk, July	6.6
90	3d wk, July	0
105	1st wk, Aug.	0
120	36 wk, Aug.	0
<i>Kharif crop 1978^b</i>		
15	1st wk, Jan.	33.3
30	3d wk, Jan.	26.6
4s	1st wk, Feb.	20.0
60	3d wk, Feb.	13.3
75	1st wk, March	6.6
90	3d wk, March	0
105	1st wk, April	0
120	3d wk, April	0

^aVirus source: infected boro crop harvested in April 1977.

^bVirus source: infected aman crop harvested in Dec. 1977.

virus source in the field. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TN1, Jaya, and Ratna

Table 2. Potential of 60-day-old rice stubble to act as the source of tungro virus in the field. 1978 kharif, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Infection (%)
Ratna	2.1
Jaya	4.0
TN1	11.5

were transplanted in 1-m² replicated plots in a randomized block design. One pot of infected stubble was placed at the center of each plot. Each plot was covered with nylon netting on wooden frames, and freshly emerged leafhoppers were released on it. The plants were observed until the booting stage, and the numbers with disease symptoms were recorded (Table 1).

The study confirmed that infected stubble can act as a virus source in the field (Table 2). Stubble can maintain the virus for 75 days in boro. But the efficiency of stubble transmission from boro stubble was lower than that from kharif stubble. The extent of transmission in both cases declined with increasing stubble age.

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Soil and crop management

Seed treatment to overcome zinc deficiency in direct-seeded rice

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Zinc deficiency in seedling rice is common in Louisiana. When recognized, it is usually corrected with a foliar application of Zn-EDTA. But in small seedlings, stands can be reduced severely before farmers recognize the problem and apply zinc.

Seed treatment with Zn-EDTA was evaluated as a means of preventing zinc

deficiency in seedling rice. Field experiments were conducted for 4 years on a Crowley silt loam soil, a Typic Haplaqualf. Soil pH was 7.6 and 0.1 N HCl extractable soil zinc was 0.5 ppm. The zinc was added to the seed by diluting a commercial 6% Zn-EDTA solution with water, adding the diluted

mixture to the seed, and tumbling to ensure thorough mixing. The rates of zinc varied each year — 0.03, 0.05, 0.06, and 0.11 kg Zn/ha were added in 1973 through 1976. The rice was drill sown at 100 kg/ha. Adequate nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were applied. The plots were mechanically harvested.

Effect of Zn-EDTA seed treatment on the yield of Vista rice, Crowley, Louisiana, USA.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	1973	1974	1975	1976	
No zinc	2.3	2.5	2.3	3.3	2.6
Zinc coated	3.0	4.1	3.3	3.9	3.6
Difference	0.7	1.6	1.0	0.6	1.0
LSD 0.05	0.4	0.7	0.4	0.7	0.3